

“Building bridges between consumers and producers by supporting short food supply chains through a systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Identification of attribute and indicators for assessment of social, economic & environmental impact

Task 2.2

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Introduction

Short food supply chains (SFSCs) can be pointed out as one of the most straightforward approaches for connecting consumers and producers in agri-food supply chains. In the academic literature SFSCs are often estimated as a more sustainable way of producing, processing, and/or selling food which demonstrates a shift to quality in both agriculture and consumption. For these reasons, within the *Farm to Fork Strategy*, short chains are recognized as a useful way for improving the resilience of regional and local food systems.

SFSCs can be understood as supply chains with a minimized number of intermediaries. The so-called golden standard could be identified in a direct contact between the producer and the consumer as a way of increasing the revenue/income for farmers/producers. But as we know, it is possible to identify many different business models, also including the sales at long distance or intermediated by digital platforms (Malak-Rawlikowska *et al.*, 2019; Todorovic *et al.*, 2020; Majewski *et al.*, 2020). In the agroBRIDGES framework a further effort in defining a synthetic categorization of different types of BMs has been carried out.

The agroBRIDGES project proposes the development of an agri-food multi-actor framework and a set of practical support tools (the agroBRIDGES Toolbox) to connect producers and consumers in new business and marketing models for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), to improve local producers market position. The decision tool identified could allow producers to fully exploit their potential in using the most appropriate model of SFSC by empowering them with knowledge that will support better decision making, improved relationship with contracting authorities and consumers, strategic alliances creation (i.e. farmers competitiveness increase and growth).

The report illustrates the path taken within the agroBRIDGES project to define a list of attributes and indicators suitable for constructing a decision-making tool to support producers in the choice of the more appropriate BM, in the light of an overall goal of sustainability. In particular, it describes how a qualitative approach has been effective in the attributes and indicators definition process given the characteristics of inclusiveness and interaction of some methods (Focus Groups and Delphi). Finally, the results obtained and the main considerations on the concrete use of such evidence is critically provided.

Methodology of the activity

The research carried out a qualitative analysis in two steps to define sustainability attributes for different BMs and a set of economic, social, and environmental indicators to provide a comprehensive sustainability assessment.

Figure 1. Interactive process for defining SFSCs attributes and indicators

Desk work and co-creation exercises with local actors has allowed to identify five different BMs categories, capable to capture many types SFCs. To investigate and analyze economic, environmental, and social aspects of the identified business and marketing models for SFSCs, a sustainability assessment model and a multicriteria decision dashboard was set, as well as the development of a decision tool.

With the aim of proposing a comprehensive sustainability assessment, information about SFSCs and their attributes have been collected first. Then a set of economic, social, and environmental indicators has been constructed based on a deeply literature review through the analysis of about 70 scientific references and other projects results such as SMARTCHAIN and STREGTH2FOOD (Bellassen et al. 2019; Bellassen et al. 2016; Antonelli and Petruzzella, 2020), which focused on assessment models and evaluation instruments to measure the economic, environmental, and social sustainability of SFSCs (Joint Research Centre, 2013; EIP AGRI, 2015).

Once these results have been organized, a logical framework was developed based on the follow chain:

Dimensions of sustainability --> Identification of attributes --> Selection of feasible indicators

where the three dimensions (economic, environmental, social) are composed by several attributes described by using different indicators.

The results of the first four stages of this process are reported in figure 3, where all relevant selected attributes and indicators are listed.

Figure 2. Logical framework

Figure 3. Initial List of Attributes and Indicators

ECONOMIC DIMENSION		ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION		SOCIAL DIMENSION	
Attributes	Suggested indicator	Attributes	Suggested indicator	Attributes	Suggested indicator
Price	Price difference Farmgate (EUR)	Carbon Footprint	Product carbon footprint	Labour	Labour to production ratio
	Price Premium (%)		Carbon footprint of production area		Labour to production ratio
	Selling price is cheaper (%)		CO ₂ emissions (lower)		Income to labour ratio
	Price obtained by producers/price paid by customer		GHG	Employment	Higher resilience of employment
Value chain and local producers sustainability	Chain value added (EUR)	Food Miles	Food Miles Total		Longer-term contracts (supply & demand side)
	Chain value added (%)		Carbon Footprint related to food miles		Number of people who can get financial benefit from SFSC
	Production costs are lower (%)		Food miles		Greater inclusion of disadvantaged people (%)
	Supply costs are lower (%)		Carbon emissions: transportation and logistic		Reduced wage difference (%)
	Distribution costs are lower (%)		Reduced food miles - km/kg production		Undesirable employee turnover rate
	Cost efficiency of delivery (€/order)		Reduced food miles - km/kg distribution	Labour / employment	Presence of corporate welfare
Impact on Farm	Turnover	Water footprint	Net Food Miles	Human Capital	Generational change
	Profit		Use of Fuel		Gender equality (%)
	Financial support		Blue water footprint		Educational attainment
	GVA		Green water footprint		Gender equality (%)
	Gross Operating Margin		Grey water footprint		No unequal treatment for same roles
	Net results				Less gender gap (%)

Sales	Reliable internet service	LCA	Global Warming	Social Capital	Public policies in agrofood sector at local/regional level are influenced by			
	Effective ordering systems,		Acidification		Local actors' way of operating is positively influenced by SFC			
	Use of social media		Eutrophication		New local networks (formal or informal) born			
	Reliable distribution		Ozone Depletion Potential		Other productive sectors are influenced by SFC			
	Use of social and environmental criteria in tenders for public procurement		Photochemical Oxidant Creation Potential		Transmissibility of knowledge and know-how			
	Procurement division into smaller lots		Non-Hazardous Waste Disposed		Presence of community welfare services to address the social needs of Spaces regenerated			
	Capacity to provide premium products	Energy consumption	Higher % of clean energy from renewable sources (%)		Relationships with customer	Customers & producers participate in		
	Special 'meet the producer' or		Reduced energy consumption (%)			Stakeholders are better involved (higher quality relations)		
	Ability to provide a large lot size and single service		More energy efficiency measures (collectively too)			Services & spaces shared		
	Strong and distinctive products	Type of process/products	Higher % of BIO products (%)			Food and Nutrition	Increased customers trust	
	Balance in market outlets		Higher % of local/traditional products (%)				Increased customers awareness	
	Collaborative hubs		Certification				Number of customers	
	Variety of sales outlets and sales routes		Production methods				Willingness to pay such kind of service	
	Affordable agricultural land close to urban population	Packaging	Less packaging is used				Governance	Increased access to food (matching local consumers with local food)
	Good interpersonal and communications skills		More eco-friendly packaging used					Accuracy and quality of the delivery service avoiding receiving broken
Key products	Food loss and waste	Reduced food loss & waste (kg)	Food and Nutrition	Following standards for food safety and control during delivery				
Regional economic impact		Number of employees		More circular economy initiatives				Potential for food traceability and level of trust-based relations between
		Number of producers involved		Food waste in distribution processes				Certification
	Geographic scale including hectares farmed			Production methods				
	Where produce is sold			Aims of the scheme (e.g. preserve				
	Local Multiplier effect			Bargaining power				
Contribution to economic (local)		Chain evaluation						
Affordability	Ability to provide food at acceptable prices (consumers sales price)			Governance	Bargaining power distribution			
	More access to ICT				Coopetion index			
	Better access to finance				SFC actors are involved in decision-			
Impact Factors	Product know-how and innovation				Governance	Customers are involved in strategic		
	Product innovation					Typology of governance is more informal		
	Collective branding					Collectively investments are made		
	Effective labelling							
	Professionalization of work							
	Technological innovations and Availability of food processing							
Bargaining power	Relationship with customers							
	Relationship with suppliers							
	Pricing - production cycle							
	Quantity of product sold							

To assess and validate this first framework of attributes and indicators, a participatory path via qualitative tools was proposed. Two rounds of DELPHI (Marbach, 1991, Hsu and Standford, 2007, Avella 2016) has been conducted in the light of assess the relevance of the attributes

identified to describes the three dimension, also operational-wise. In parallel, two online Focus Groups (Morgan, 2018) were set, one with experts involved in the agroBRIDGES Stakeholder Reference Group¹ and one with experts from other projects on SFSCs², in order to select the more suitable and feasible indicators to design the assessment model (RACER criteria).

The results of both research activities were analyzed using quantitative (statistical analysis for the Delphi survey) and qualitative (content analysis for the focus groups) methods.

Results of Focus Groups and Delphi Rounds

The early evidence highlighted at least three elements for discussion, relevant in theoretical and operational terms.

The main challenge was to identify an information set as feasible, simple, and homogeneous as possible. On the one hand, despite a copious literature on the topic, only few references offer indication for a concrete evaluation of SFSCs in operational terms. Very often only theoretical reflections are reported, and dimensions and attributes of analysis are proposed. Only in rare cases a real attempt of quantifying these dimensions is observed. Where quantifications have been possible, information gaps are observed in a spatial or temporal sense which can invalidate the models. In this sense, also the quality of the data, in terms of robustness, has to be evaluated. We can estimate a tradeoff between cost and difficulty of collection and feasibility. In many cases, the literature refers to self-assessment procedures to ensure the feasibility of collection, but this leads to a reduction in the reliability of the information.

The observation of the strengths and weaknesses of the performance matrix brings to the forefront the need to compose a simple evaluation model that can be managed all by producers, to whom the decisional tool is addressed, as suggested by the experts involved in the Delphi survey and Focus groups. The main constraint remains the feasibility of the basic information, i.e., the concrete possibility of collecting the indicators that make up the various attributes and thus the three main dimensions.

To address these constraints, several solutions can be identified, including the option to overcome the mandatory requirement to populate all identified indicators, allowing the adoption of a "Pick and Choose" model, where one could choose only the indicators supported by available data.

The participatory methods (Delphi and Focus Group) have allowed to test results and alternative options. The outcomes show a high level of agreement among the opinions, with some minor exceptions, on the proposed attributes and indicators.

¹ agroBRIDGES Stakeholder Reference Group is composed by one representative per each State participant as well as other stakeholders from the Experts Advisory Board and from EU agri-food community.

² Experts from COACH, FOODRUS, and COCOREADO participated in the Focus Group.

Regarding the measurement of the economic sustainability of SFSCs through the proposed attributes (price, value distribution, farm economic results, regional economic impact and bargaining power) there was a good level of agreement in the responses. Although there are fewer disagreements and neutral values, mainly about the attribute price and about bargaining power and regional economic impact. Some relevant suggestions can be highlighted to simplify the collection of indicators, especially at the level of impact on farms (e.g. turnover instead of value added).

About the measurement of the environmental sustainability of SFSCs described by the proposed attributes (food miles, energy consumption, type of production process and food L&W) there was a quite high level of agreement among respondents. However, the presence of some neutral opinions about food L&W, a mix of disagreements and neutral opinions about type of production process (particularly on “certification” indicator) and finally some degree of disagreement about food miles attribute must be underlined.

Concerning the social sustainability described through the attributes, the experts involved in the focus groups mentioned the difficulty of measuring and handle the dimension, but at the same time the willingness to understand the impacts of short supply chain using the attributes labour/employment, human capital, social capital, food & nutrition and governance of food system. Also, the need to think "out of the gate of the farm", trying to understand and measure the social capital through, for example, the capacity to build networks, to involve stakeholders in the activities (i.e. for CSA) was highlighted. In this sense, the farmer is a relevant actor in the territory, being part of the decision-making process. The suggestion to consider the importance of territorial networks and the consolidation and cohesion of actors also came out.

Final List of Attributes and Indicators

Starting from the analysis of the results of the Delphi, the level of agreement or disagreement reached was assessed for each indicator, following the following steps of judgement: first Delphi round and second one; first and second Focus Group. These evaluations were expressed with a sort of traffic light: green: the indicator was accepted; red: the indicator was rejected; yellow: the indicator should be re-evaluated. From the initial list of indicators proposed in the Delphi survey and Focus Groups, 47 items were determined, condensed into 14 attributes, along the three main dimensions.

In addition, for each attribute a Lead Indicator was estimated, which has a mandatory character in the composition of the attribute, while the other proposed indicators could also not be used in case the collection is too difficult or even not possible.

The findings have also been summarized in a so-called performance matrix, to relate the BMs to the attributes.

Figure 4. Final List of Attributes and Indicators

Price
Price difference Farmgate
Price Premium
Value chain and local producers sustainability
Chain value added
Chain value added
Production costs are lower
Supply costs are lower
Equity in the value generated
Impact on Farm
Turnover
Financial support
Production costs
Distribution costs
Access to credit
Regional economic impact
Number of employees
Number of producers involved
Sells to local customers
Local supply
Bargaining power
Relationship with customers
Relationship with suppliers
Bargaining power Self-Assessment

Food Miles
Carbon Footprint related to food miles
Reduced food miles (production and distribution)
Use of Fuel
Energy consumption
Reduced energy consumption
More energy efficiency measures
Type of process/Products/Packaging
% of BIO products
% of local/traditional products
Access to agri-environmental schemes support
More eco-friendly packaging used
Food loss and waste
Reduced food loss & waste
More circular economy initiatives

Labour/Employment
Labour to production ratio
Presence of corporate welfare
Higher resilience of employment
Inclusion of disadvantaged people
Human capital
Generational change
Educational attainment
Gender equality
No unequal treatment for same roles
Social capital
Influence by SFSC
New local networks
Customers & producers participation
Stakeholders' involvement
Food and Nutrition
Increased access to food via SFSC
Standards for food safety
Increased customers awareness
Governance
Coopetion index
SFSC actors' proactive involvement

Note: Lead indicators are in bold

Figure 5. List of attributes by category of BM: Performance matrix

CSA	FACE to FACE TRADE	LOCAL FOOD TRADE	ONLINE FOOD TRADE	IMPROVED LOGISTICS
Price	Price	Price	Price	Price
Value chain and local producers' sustainability				
Impact on Farm				
Regional economic impact		Regional economic impact		Regional economic impact
Bargaining power	Bargaining power	Bargaining power		Bargaining power
Food Miles		Food Miles		
Energy consumption				
Type of process/ products / Packaging				
Food loss and waste				
Labour / employment				
Human capital				
Social capital	Social capital	Social capital		Social capital
	Food and Nutrition			Food and Nutrition
Governance		Governance	Governance	Governance

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Annex 1
Delphi Questionnaires

agroBRIDGES questionnaire

The agroBRIDGES team is pleased to invite you to participate as experts in Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) Delphi Survey. The aim of this activity is to define a set of attribute and indicators to evaluate social, economic, and environmental sustainability of SFSCs for producers.

The survey include two rounds: you should answer to this questionnaire and, in a few weeks, to another one built on the basis of the results of this data collection.

*Campo obbligatorio

1. Email *

Sezione senza titolo

2. I agree to participate in the Delphi survey and consent to the processing of data for the purpose of the survey *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes

No *Vai alla sezione 7 (Thank you for participating).*

SFSCs economic sustainability

3. 1. The SFSCs economic sustainability can be described through these attributes. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Price	<input type="radio"/>				
Value distribution along the chain	<input type="radio"/>				
Farm economic results	<input type="radio"/>				
Regional economic impact	<input type="radio"/>				
Bargaining power	<input type="radio"/>				

4. 2. Use this space if you think there are more attributes to describe the SFSCs economic sustainability. Please, specify indicators and references for each additional proposed attribute. Also use this space for any comments.

5. 3. In your opinion, how feasible are the proposed SFSCs' economic sustainability attributes for assessment of the following business models? For each business model, tick the attributes that you consider feasible. *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

	Price	Value distribution along the chain	Farm economic results	Regional economic impact	Bargaining power
CSA (Community Supported Agriculture)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
On Farm Sales	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Off Farm Sales - Commercial Sector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Off Farm Sales - Catering sector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm Direct Deliveries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

SFSCs environmental sustainability

6. 4. The SFSCs environmental sustainability can be described through these attributes. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Food Miles	<input type="radio"/>				
Energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
Type of production process	<input type="radio"/>				
Food loss and waste	<input type="radio"/>				

7. 5. Use this space if you think there are more attributes to describe the SFSCs environmental sustainability. Please, specify indicators and references for each additional proposed attribute. Also use this space for any comments.

8. 6. In your opinion, how feasible are the proposed SFSCs' environmental sustainability attributes for assessment of the following business models? For each business model, tick the attributes that you consider feasible. *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

	Food Miles	Energy consumption	Type of production process	Food loss and waste
CSA (Community Supported Agriculture)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
On Farm Sales	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Off Farm Sales - Commercial Sector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Off Farm Sales - Catering sector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm Direct Deliveries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

SFSCs social sustainability

9. 7. The SFSCs social sustainability can be described through these attributes. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Labour/employment	<input type="radio"/>				
Human capital	<input type="radio"/>				
Social capital	<input type="radio"/>				
Food and Nutrition	<input type="radio"/>				
Governance of food system	<input type="radio"/>				

10. 8. Use this space if you think there are more attributes to describe the SFSCs social sustainability. Please, specify indicators and references for each additional proposed attribute. Also use this space for any comments.

11. 9. In your opinion, how feasible are the proposed SFSCs' social sustainability attributes for assessment of the following business models? For each business model, tick * the attributes that you consider feasible

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

	Labour/employment	Human capital	Social capital	Food and Nutrition	Governance of food system
CSA (Community Supported Agriculture)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
On Farm Sales	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Off Farm Sales - Commercial sector	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Off Farm Sales - Catering sector	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Farm Direct Deliveries	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Pick and choose

12. 10. A single attribute could be measured by the aggregation of different proposed indicators. For example, PRICE attribute (SFSCs economic sustainability) can be measured through: Price difference Farmgate (EUR) Price Premium (%) Selling price is cheaper (%). The golden standard is that all proposed indicators are populated; however, necessary data may not be available in all countries and / or all cases. For facing the possible criticality of data gap, we propose also the option to choose and use even a single indicator among those available (Pick and Choose option). Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement about the "Pick and Choose" option.

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Using "Pick and Choose"	<input type="radio"/>				

Thank you for participating

agroBRIDGES questionnaire

The agroBRIDGES team is pleased to invite you to participate as experts in Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) to the 2nd round of a Delphi Survey. The aim of this activity is to define a set of attributes and indicators to evaluate social, economic, and environmental sustainability of SFSCs for producers. This in-depth survey has been developed on the basis of the results of the first round data collection. Thank you for your cooperation.

*Campo obbligatorio

1. Email *

2. I agree to participate in the Delphi survey and consent to the processing of data for the purpose of the survey *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes

No Vai alla sezione 5 (Thank you for participating).

1 - SFSCs economic sustainability

3. 1a. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the PRICE attribute of SFSC economic sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Price difference Farmgate (EUR)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Price Premium (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cheaper selling price (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. 1b. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the BARGAINING POWER attribute of SFSC economic sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Relationship with customers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Relationship with suppliers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantity of product sold	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bargaining power Self -Assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. 1c. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the REGIONAL ECONOMIC IMPACT attribute of SFSC economic sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Number of employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Number of producers involved	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Geographic scale including hectares farmed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sells to local customers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local supply	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2 - SFSCs environmental sustainability

6. 2a. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the FOOD MILES attribute of SFSC environmental sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Reduced food miles - km/kg production	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduced food miles - km/kg distribution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food Miles (distance travelled in km)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Use of Fuel	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher % of clean energy from renewable sources (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. 2b. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the TYPE OF PRODUCTION PROCESS attribute of SFSC environmental sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Higher % of BIO products (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher % of local/traditional products (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Presence of certification (i.e. organic, PDO, PGI, TSG, ecc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Less packaging is used	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3 - SFSCs social sustainability

8. 3a. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the LABOUR/EMPLOYMENT attribute of SFSC social sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Labour to product ratio (number of annual work unit per ton of product)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Labour to production ratio (AWU.t-1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Corporate and community welfare actions/services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher resilience of employment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Greater inclusion of disadvantaged people (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduced wage difference (%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. 3b. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the GOVERNANCE OF FOOD SYSTEM attribute of SFSC social sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Coopetition index (it accounts the balance between cooperation-oriented and competition-oriented behaviors)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
SFC actors are involved in decision-making processes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Typology of governance is more informal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collective investments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Type and number of actors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. 3c. Indicate to what extent the following indicators are appropriate measures of the FOOD AND NUTRITION attribute of SFSC social sustainability *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Increased access to food (matching local consumers with local food)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Following standards for food safety and control during delivery	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Presence of certification (i.e. organic, PDO, PGI, TSG, ecc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increased customers awareness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. 4. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the following attributes for the assessment of CSA (Community Supported Agriculture) business model's sustainability. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Price	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Value distribution along the chain	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regional economic impact	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bargaining power	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food nutrition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. 5. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the following attributes for the assessment of On Farm Sales business model's sustainability. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Value distribution along the chain	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bargaining power	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food miles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Governance of food system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food nutrition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. 6. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the following attributes for the assessment of Off Farm Sales - Commercial Sector business model's sustainability. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Price	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regional economic impact	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Human capital	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social capital	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food nutrition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Governance of food system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. 7. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the following attributes for the assessment of Off Farm Sales - Catering Sector business model's sustainability. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Price	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regional economic impact	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bargaining power	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food miles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Governance of food system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. 8. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the following attributes for the assessment of Farm Direct Delivery business model's sustainability. *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Value distribution along the chain	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regional economic impact	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food miles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food nutrition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Governance of food system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. 9. A single attribute could be measured by the aggregation of different proposed indicators. For example, PRICE attribute (SFSCs economic sustainability) can be measured through: Price difference Farmgate (EUR), Price Premium (%), Cheaper selling price (%). The golden standard is that all proposed indicators are populated; however, necessary data may not be available in all countries and / or all cases. For facing the possible criticality of data gap, there are different options. Indicate the level of agreement or disagreement about the options *

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
All for one approach: where the whole set of indicators is quantifiable in each countries (mandatory).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harvest time approach: choosing only some indicators in an attribute, i.e. only those considered necessary and therefore to be quantified ("mandatory"), and the others could be optional.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The pick and choose approach: choosing and using a single indicator among those proposed, taking into account the availability of data and information in each different country.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thank you for participating

Questi contenuti non sono creati né avallati da Google.

Google Moduli

Annex 2
Delphi tables

Annex 2: Delphi results

The annex presents the empirical statistics about respondents through three heat maps for delphi round 1 and one for delphi round 2 related to the three dimensions of sustainability considered.

A heat map is a graphical representation of data where values are depicted by colour. The different colours represent each one a scale score used in the collection of data: green for “strongly agree”, yellow for “agree”, white for “neutral”, orange for “disagree” and red for “strongly disagree”.

Delphi Round 1

Economic Sustainability Results

ID	[Price]	[Value distribution along the chain]	[Farm economic results]	[Regional economic impact]	[Bargaining power]
1	3	3	3	-3	3
2	5	5	3	5	5
3	3	5	3		5
4		5	5	5	3
5	-3	5	5	3	
6		3	3	3	3
7	3	5	5	3	3
8	5	3	5		
9	3	5	3	3	-3
10		5	3	5	3
11	-5	5	5	3	-3
12	3	5	3		5
13	3	5	3	5	5
14	3	5	5	3	-3
15		3	3		
16	3	5	3	3	3
17	-3	3	5	5	5
18		5	3		3
19	3	5		5	5

Environmental Sustainability Results

ID	[Food Miles]	[Energy consumption]	[Type of production process]	[Food loss and waste]
1		3	3	3
2	5	5	5	5
3	3			3
4	-3	-3	3	
5	5	3	-3	
6	3	3	3	
7	3	5	5	3
8	5	3	5	5
9		3	-3	3
10	3	5	-3	3
11	-3	5		5
12	5	5		3
13	3	5	5	5
14	-3	5	5	5
15	3		3	
16	3	3	5	5
17	-5	3	3	3
18	-3	-3	5	
19	5	5	3	3

Social Sustainability Results

ID	[Labour/em ployment]	[Human capital]	[Social capital]	[Food and Nutrition]	[Governance of food system]
1	3	3	3	5	
2	5	5	5		5
3		3	3	3	
4	5	5	5	5	5
5		3	3	3	5
6	5	5	5	3	3
7	5	3	3	3	5
8	5	5	5	5	5
9		3	5	3	-3
10	3	5	5	5	5
11					
12	3	3	3	3	3
13	5	5	5	5	5
14	5	5	5	3	5
15	3	3	5	5	
16	3	5	5	5	5
17	3	3	5		3
18			5	5	5
19	5	5	5	3	5

Polarisation of Results

ID	Neutral	Strongly agree	Disagree
1	2	1	1
2	1	12	0
3	5	2	0
4	2	8	2
5	3	6	2
6	2	3	0
7	0	6	0
8	2	10	0
9	2	2	3
10	1	7	1
11	6	4	2
12	2	4	0
13	0	11	0
14	0	9	2
15	6	2	0
16	0	7	0
17	1	4	1
18	5	5	2
19	1	9	0

Delphi Round 2

Attribute	Indicator	strongly agree	agree	disagree	strongly disagree
PRICE	PRICE DIFFERENCE FARMGATE (EUR)	3	7	3	
	PRICE PREMIUM (%)	7	5	1	
	CHEAPER SELLING PRICE (%)		1	9	3
BARGAINING POWER	RELATIONSHIP WITH CUSTOMERS	3	8	2	
	RELATIONSHIP WITH SUPPLIERS	4	5	4	
	QUANTITY OF PRODUCT SOLD	1	4	6	2
	BARGAINING POWER SELF-ASSESSMENT	2	9	2	
REGIONAL ECONOMIC IMPACT	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	3	10		
	NUMBER OF PRODUCERS INVOLVED	4	8	1	
	GEOGRAPHIC SCALE INCLUDING HECTARES FARMED	2	7	3	1
	SELLS TO LOCAL CUSTOMERS	1	8	4	
	LOCAL SUPPLY	1	12		
FOOD MILES	REDUCED FOOD MILES KM/KG PRODUCTION	2	8	2	1
	REDUCED FOOD MILES KM/KG DISTRIBUTION	1	9	2	1
	FOOD MILES DISTANCE TRAVELLED IN KM	1	7	3	2
	USE OF FUEL	4	6	3	
	HIGHER % OF CLEAN ENERGY FROM RENEWABLE SOURCES (%)	2	6	4	1
TYPE OF PRODUCTION PROCESS	HIGHER % OF BIO PRODUCTS (%)	6	6	1	
	HIGHER % OF LOCAL/TRADITIONAL PRODUCTS (%)	2	8	3	
	PRESENCE OF CERTIFICATION (i.e. organic, PDO, PGI, TSG, etc.)	1	6	5	1
	LESS PACKAGING IS USED	2	6	5	
LABOUR/EMPLOYMENT	LABOUR TO PRODUCT RATIO (number of annual work unit per ton of product)	2	8	3	
	LABOUR TO PRODUCT RATIO (AWU.t-1)	2	6	5	
	CORPORATE AND COMMUNITY WELFARE ACTIONS/SERVICES	3	6	4	
	HIGHER RESILIENCE OF EMPLOYMENT	4	6	3	
	GREATER INCLUSION OF DISADVANTAGED PEOPLE (%)	3	9	1	
	REDUCED WAGE DIFFERENCE (%)	1	8	4	
GOVERNANCE OF FOOD SYSTEM	COOPERATION INDEX (it accounts the balance between cooperation-oriented and competition-oriented behaviours)	3	7	3	
	SFC ACTORS ARE INVOLVED IN DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES	4	8	1	
	TYPOLOGY OF GOVERNANCE IS MORE INFORMAL		3	9	1
	COLLECTIVE INVESTMENTS	5	4	4	
	TYPE AND NUMBER OF ACTORS	1	7	5	
FOOD AND NUTRITION	INCREASED ACCESS TO FOOD (MATCHING LOCAL CONSUMERS WITH LOCAL FOOD)	2	8	3	
	DELIVERY	2	9	2	
	PRESENCE OF CERTIFICATION (i.e. organic, PDO, PGI, TSG, etc.)		9	4	
	INCREASED CUSTOMERS AWARENESS	5	7	1	

Annex 3
Focus Groups Factsheets

INTRODUCTION

The 1st Focus Group on “*Identification of attributes for the assessment of SFSCs' social, economic and environmental impact*” took place online on 14th January 2022, coordinated by CREA - Council for Agricultural Research and Economics.

Experts in SFSC and SRG members took part with the objective to discuss and assess the feasibility of the identified and proposed set of attributes and indicators characterizing the social, economic and environmental dimensions of SFSCs, built within task 2.2 activities.

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The focus group took place online, on TEAMS platform, involving a total of 13 participants, including 6 experts SRG members, 7 researchers from agroBRIDGES WP2 working group.

The event, organized and moderated by CREA, started with a brief presentation of the activity and followed by a round table of presentations. The discussion on attributes and indicators has been launched by a power point presentation concerning task 2.2 activities.

The open discussion about social, economic and environmental attributes and indicators of SFSC has been moderated by CREA using the online application "mentimeter", providing a smooth and easier interaction among participants and enabling coordinators and experts to display on screen comments, ideas, opinions on each group of indicators presented. The debate revealed a general agreement on the attributes and indicators presented and a need to simplify the assessment criteria making them understandable for the end-users (producers) avoiding unwelcome correlation, together with some new inputs to be considered. Understanding the feasibility of indicators presented was the main driving force of the discussion. Main outcomes from the discussion are presented hereafter.

1ST GROUP OF INDICATORS - ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 1st group discussed concerns the economic sustainability of SFSCs.

The five attributes presented with their different indicators are: *PRICE, VALUE CHAIN & LOCAL PRODUCERS SUSTAINABILITY, IMPACT ON FARM, BARGAINING POWER, REGIONAL ECONOMIC IMPACT*. Experts agreed with the chosen attributes and indicators. Key outcomes from the discussion included the *need to simplify indicators* to allow an immediate and successful use by farmers and to *pay attention on cross-cutting and territorial values* as well as *individuality*. Some doubts arose on the indicator "*Gross Value Added (GVA)*", mainly because of the difficulty of being measured. A proposal concerned the possibility to add an indicator measuring the *equal distribution of value along the supply chain*. An additional suggestion concerned the possibility to find an indicator (which can be linked also to the environmental dimension) related to the *climate adaptation of the farm*.

2ND GROUP OF INDICATORS - ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 2nd group discussed concerns the environmental sustainability of SFSCs.

The four main attributes presented with their different indicators are: *FOOD MILES, ENERGY CONSUMPTION, TYPE OF PROCESS/PROD/PACKAGING, FOOD L&W*. Experts agreed with the indicators and attributes chosen. An interesting discussion concerned the "*food miles*" which resulted to be the most controversial for its non-unique understanding.

Among the main discussion outcomes we find the need to take into account the issues related to transportation; the suggestion to *consider not only the carbon footprint but the ecological footprint* (considering that measuring the carbon footprint at farm level could be very difficult and expensive in terms of skills for a farmer); the suggestion to reduce the two attributes "*reduced food miles km/kg production*" and "*km/kg distribution*" into one in order to avoid farmers' confusion. Another suggestion concerns the *consideration of the methods of production* (organic or not, for instance) together with the concept of food miles. An example was shared demonstrating that within a certain geographical range, the production method is more influential in terms of environmental impact compared to the distance over which the product is transported. Also, the opportunity to have some indicators related to *water consumption, biodiversity* and also the *impact of animal breeding* (animal per hectare) came out.

3RD GROUP OF INDICATORS - SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 3rd group discussed concerns the **social sustainability** of SFSCs.

The five attributes presented with their different indicators are: *LABOUR/EMPLOYMENT, HUMAN CAPITAL, SOCIAL CAPITAL, FOOD AND NUTRITION, GOVERNANCE*.

Experts agreed with the indicators and attributes chosen. Among the main discussion outcomes, there was a *shared awareness about the difficulty of measuring and handle the social dimension*, but at the same time the *willingness to understand the impacts of short chain models on human capital, gender equality, education, and so on*. Also, the need to *think "out of the gate of the farm"*, trying to understand and measure the capacity to build networks and to involve stakeholders in the activities (for CSA, for example), but also to be a relevant subject and voice in the territory, being part of the decision making process.

The suggestion to *consider the importance of territorial networks and the consolidation and cohesion of actors* came out. A proposition on the possibility to find a way to measure the inclusion and involvement of vulnerable and disadvantaged social groups also emerged.

INTRODUCTION

The 2nd Focus Group on “Identification of attributes for the assessment of SFSCs' social, economic and environmental impact” took place online on 21st January 2022, coordinated by CREA - Council for Agricultural Research and Economics. 7 participants (experts in SFSCs) took part with the objective to discuss and assess the feasibility of the identified and proposed set of attributes and indicators characterizing the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of SFSCs, built through task 2.2 activities.

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The focus group took place online, on TEAMS platform, involving a total of 11 participants, including 7 experts involved in agroBRIDGES sister projects and 4 researchers from CREA working group. The event started with a brief presentation of the activity and followed by a round table of presentations. The discussion on indicators and attributes has been launched by a power point presentation concerning task 2.2 activities.

The open discussion about social, economic, and environmental attributes and indicators of SFSC has been moderated by CREA using the online application "mentimeter", providing a smooth and easier interaction among participants and enabling coordinators and experts to display on screen comments, ideas, opinions on each group of indicators presented. As in the first focus, the debate revealed a general agreement on the attributes and indicators presented and a need to simplify the assessment criteria making them understandable for the intended users (producers) avoiding unwelcome correlation, together with some new inputs to be considered, especially concerning the economic dimension. Understanding the feasibility of indicators presented was the main driving force of the discussion as in the first focus group. Main outcomes from the debate are presented hereafter.

1ST GROUP OF INDICATORS - ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 1st group discussed concerns the economic sustainability of SFSCs.

The five attributes presented with their different indicators are: *PRICE, VALUE CHAIN & LOCAL PRODUCERS SUSTAINABILITY, IMPACT ON FARM, BARGAINING POWER, REGIONAL ECONOMIC IMPACT*. Even though experts generally agreed with the chosen attributes and indicators, many interesting inputs came out from the discussion, among which the *difficulty in measuring GVA at farm level* (farmers could experience some difficulties in measuring it) as well as regarding *costs and benefits* (from experts' point of view, farmers don't usually have a precise idea of costs and benefits data). *Turnover resulted to be an easier indicator for the farmers' self-assessment*. Another suggestion concerned the attribute "*regional economic impact*" for which some assessment issues could arise when asking a single farmer/producer to measure something out of their own farm/business. A reflection on its feasibility came out. An additional comment concerned the *reduction of indicators related to "costs"*, which are present in more than one attribute, trying to avoid overlapping. In this sense, it is worth noting that the farmers/producers could do the assessment by choosing the indicators most convenient for their context and for which they could provide reliable data (*pick&choose method*). Also, a *consideration on the variability of prices* has been given, with a remark on their not exhaustive capacity to assess profitability of farmers. For this reason, *a self-assessment on the perception of income has been suggested as more successful* (even though producers have data and notions on prices) with a feasible indicator such as "*impact on income/family income*". At the same time, a suggestion concerned the issue of *prices stability*: experts agreed that considering the stability of prices could be more useful and important for a sustainability assessment. The issue of including in the framework the production costs and monetary losses of unharvested products or, more generally, of food losses and waste, was also discussed, together with the need to better explain the concept of "*bargaining power*", enabling farmers to easily understand and evaluate.

2ND GROUP OF INDICATORS - ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 2nd group discussed concerns the **environmental sustainability** of SFSCs.

The four main attributes presented with their different indicators are: *FOOD MILES, ENERGY CONSUMPTION, TYPE OF PROCESS/PROD/PACKAGING, FOOD L&W*. Experts generally agreed with the indicators and attributes chosen.

Among the main discussion outcomes, we found the need to consider the *issues related to the biodiversity and agrobiodiversity preservation* and the contributions made by SFSCs to it; the possibility to add an indicator referring to the *territorial management of landscapes* - many farmers are conscious and engaged in preserving the territory from land degradation and other threats, so it could be interesting for a sustainability self-assessment. Also, the need to clarify which is the *benchmark of the assessment for the farmer* (explaining if they are assessing what happens in SFSC in comparison with what happens in long chains or in relation to other farmers or previous situations not related to SFSC, etc.). Some other resulted inputs concerned the *"Food loss and waste"* attribute, which could include both the ability to prevent and to deal with food losses and waste at farm level; the suggestion to also consider the *consumers' point of view* when dealing with *"reduced food miles km/kg distribution"* (the controversial nature of the attribute *"food miles"* due to its non-unique understanding emerged also in this 2nd focus group). An interesting advice concerned the *possibility to remove completely the indicator "certification"* which being characterized by so many schemes, would make harder and not very clear the farmers' self-assessment.

do not forget the contribution to biodiversity preservation	impact on territorial management/landscapes: many farmers involved in preserving the territory from land degradation/etc.: could be interesting to add an attribute on this	Prevent and reduce FLW
the (lower?) use of plastics is a big societal issue		certification: taking into account context differences
consider an indicator on land/water management, landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity	the indicator "more circular econ initiatives" not so clear - suggestion: how to deal with food waste in the farm	animal welfare?
	what type of energy (fossil, renewable) is used on the farm	
food miles: the distribution should be considered also from the consumers' side	% increased number of local/seasonal/organic/ugly food	divide into - food loss and waste prevention and means to reduce food waste through other means
using access to rural development plan can be tricky. Many farmers participating to SFSCs never had aids from RDP, due to their limited dimension, or because they are not "professional" ones, or even costs /procedures to access RDP	it would be relevant to list several good agroecological practices (green manures, etc.)	

3RD GROUP OF INDICATORS - SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF SFSC

The 3rd group discussed concerns the **social sustainability** of SFSCs.

The five attributes presented with their different indicators are: *LABOUR/EMPLOYMENT, HUMAN CAPITAL, SOCIAL CAPITAL, FOOD AND NUTRITION, GOVERNANCE*.

Experts generally agreed with the indicators and attributes chosen. Among the main discussion outcomes, the suggestion to include some indicators related to *digital solutions* (not only online sales and shop, but also on a logistics point of view). In terms of labour, the *concept of seasonality* should be considered. Another proposal for the “*governance*” aspect regarded the suggestion to keep in mind if some legal framework constraints exist (in addition to administrative barriers) slowing down or preventing farmers in their activities.

An additional outcome concerned the concept of “*stability*” which should be considered also within the social dimension (with a different perspective compared to the economic one): for example, how the farm is engaged on creating and sharing knowledge on what local food systems are or, more generally, in reshaping the local food consumption, organizing educational events, etc. The indicator “*increase customers awareness*” in this sense could be considered broad and general and so, difficult to understand. For the *F&N* attribute, a suggestion for including the aspect of “*access to healthy food for lower income consumers*” emerged, which could be included into the more general “*increase access to food*” indicator. “*Collective Investments*” indicator could be transferred into the economic dimension and, more generally, turned into “*higher possibility to cooperate/activate collaborations with other producers/stakeholders/institutions at a local level*”. Talking about labour and work, an important aspect which should be studied is the *quality of work* (farmers’ self-esteem, way to sell and interact with consumers in these channels, etc.). Another interesting aspect which could be considered in the social sustainability assessment is the gender of the agricultural entrepreneur, useful to analyze a series of gender related issues. A general simplification of the concepts provided has been suggested (*more direct and simple questions to be understood*).

suggestion to add digital solutions

but digital solutions also create new dependencies on technology providers so beware

Will there be a definition of 'disadvantaged people'? People can be disadvantaged in a range of different ways...

